

**Recommendations and Research Gaps
to Improve the Function of the
Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) concept:
SETAC – EC Consultation series 2023-24**

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Background: This document is a summary of key conceptual and practical opportunities to improve the utility, comprehensiveness and validity of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) assessments, along with the resulting research gaps, which were identified based on the outcomes of a series of online and in-person consultations with the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) scientific community, undertaken in 2023 and 2024. The focus is on further development of SSbD-methods for the chemical sector, expanding on ongoing work in the European Union carried out over the past 2 years. Detailed descriptions of the process and findings underpinning this document can be found in the detailed consultation reports¹. Priority research gaps were extracted from the consultations' results and combined into a limited set of priority considerations and recommendations, seeking to improve the principles and practices of SSbD approaches.

Purpose: The present document provides a concise outline of major research gaps identified, following a request made by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (EC DG RTD) to the sounding board supporting SETAC-Europe's membership of the EC High Level Round Table for the Implementation of the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability. It aims to supplement the EC's SSbD-guidance report by Abbate et al. (2024) and further support the ongoing work, including that under PARC. This document only covers the Environmental (E) aspects of SSbD and does not touch on social (S) or governance (G) aspects, which would require a separate analysis by experts in these respective fields.

Contextual recommendation 1: Reuse the science for multiple purposes across the EU legislations.

The SSbD-vision is central to reaching the EU's Green Deal aspirations in connection with its Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), such as the zero pollution aim and the goal of ensuring the long term sustainability of the chemical sector in Europe. The Green Deal has led to a series of policy instruments (*e.g.*, Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR); European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS); Digital Product Passport (DPP); Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD); Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)), which the SSbD should support and facilitate in order to enable a timely delivery on the Green Deal's ambition to attain a sustainable transition of the EU market. That is, it is recognized that results of the priority research themes should support both the SSbD-based design of novel chemicals and products as well as provide a basis to evaluate efficacy and progress upon implementation via the aforementioned evaluation frameworks and their reporting approaches and needs. Hence, the identified SSbD-related research gaps should be implementable in a versatile manner to support the development of comprehensive sets of practical, regulatory, and policy instruments, in order to properly deliver on the Green Deal's objectives.

Contextual recommendation 2: Prioritise the SSbD efforts to focus on the most promising areas first.

A key priority is to identify the critical impact categories. Resources must be deployed to sort these out. What is the method to find the top three to five impact categories that drive the sustainability score/ classification of substances or products? Research on chemical pollution problems in the field consistently shows results in the form of sites and chemicals causing the highest share of health or environmental problems, along with the most significant impact pathways contributing to that, for both safety and/or sustainability impact categories. This pattern, emerging from available data and studies on safety and sustainability impact categories, can be further and systematically substantiated to help

¹ Links to these reports are provided at the end of this report.

prioritise cases and/or applications where SSbD-guided assessment and innovation would be most effective.

Data generation: Research gaps 1 and 2

Research gap 1: Develop New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) to fill current voids . Assessment and comparison of safe and sustainable products/substances in SSbD should include a proper consideration of the long-term, chronic effects. However, currently the majority of NAMs only consider the short-term endpoints. The research should focus on the development of fit-for-purpose chronic NAMs (e.g., reprotoxicity) which could replace *in vivo* animal endpoints. Robust NAMs, both *in silico* and *in vitro*, should be included. These can be used, independently or together, at different technology readiness levels (TRL), and can serve to inform the innovation process. A faster evaluation / qualification / validation process should be proposed to ensure the assessments are based on state-of-the-art science and can thus help to reduce the gap between science and regulatory application.

There is moreover a lack of *in silico* and/or rapid *in vitro* methods to accurately predict degradation in a time- and cost-efficient way necessary to inform innovation processes, especially for mixtures. Hence, this also needs to be developed. Associated with the opportunities and characteristics of well-designed tiered approaches (see Research gap 3), research should seek to enhance consistency in the results of SSbD assessments undertaken across the innovation steps, up to the point of final decision-making. Finally, the NAMs considered should also address upscaling extrapolation to ecosystems and landscapes in an adverse outcome pathway (AOP) context. TRL (Technology Readiness Levels) 2-5.²

Research gap 2: Develop and validate Artificial Intelligence (AI) for SSbD. Novel AI-based principles, approaches, and tools are needed to support the access to and integration of data for safety and sustainability impact metrics. Provision of these data should be open source ensuring FAIR data access. Early-stage innovation steps are characterised by data gaps or data absence. AI-based methods should provide latitude to fill data gaps, for both safety and sustainability impact metrics. Initial results obtained for hazard assessment show that this specific form of NAMs, capable of using the body of existing data to provide insights into missing data on SSbD-relevant aspects, may hold vast potential for advancing data generation for SSbD-assessment purposes. However, it needs to be highlighted that validation is currently considered to be a key challenge in AI-based SSbD research. TRL 2-4.

Methodological frameworks: Research gaps 3 and 4

Research gap 3: Prioritisation of next-generation Product Environmental Footprint (PEF/EF) methodology and its adaptation to the chemical sector. Approaches to prioritisation of the PEF categories for novel chemicals or products are needed, as scientific evidence shows that there are typically a few key drivers among several sustainability metrics/ endpoints that determine final SSbD-outcomes for a particular product. Directly associated with this, scoring and weighting these would enable a more accurate sustainability scoring, with accuracy being confirmed by case-studies and evaluation / validation processes. In order to handle data-poor situations typical for early stages of innovation, a tiered data requirement and analysis system should be developed for each category to

² The Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) are broad indications of distance to realization. The higher the TRL level, the less time is estimated to be needed until implementation.

ensure proportionality in the requirements - ranging from fast and conservative (SME and early innovation stages) to comprehensive and accurate (large companies and later “ready to market” stages) indicators - and including, but not limited to, NAMs-based testing. Thus, scientific methods must be developed and implemented to identify and prioritise relevant PEF impact categories for the SSbD assessment at hand, to develop accurate tiering for all impact categories, to weigh the obtained results given the multi-dimensionality of interim- and final outputs, and to ensure that the SSbD-characterisation is validated. The research should recognize that chemicals often co-occur as mixtures in products and processes, and ultimately in the end-of-life phase, in nature, requiring mixtures to be addressed. TRL 2-5.

Research gap 4: Next generation LCA methodologies: Complement the SSbD assessment to cover all relevant aspects in a balanced and effective way. Efficacy can be improved and balanced through development and integration of tiered risk assessment methodologies into a life cycle assessment (LCA) approach. Relevance and comprehensiveness of SSbD-results need to be improved via the development of novel LCAs for key areas of interest. In addition to the social-LCA (S-LCA), these should address: 1) GHG emissions (GHG-LCA); 2) Waste and pollution (WP-LCA); 3) Biodiversity (BIODIV-LCA); 4) Water (WAT-LCA); 5) Circularity (CIR-LCA). The LCAs should range from cradle-to-gate and all the way to cradle-to-cradle level of detail as needed in the innovation process and the product. A need for expansion of the S-LCA approaches was also identified. Appropriate tools for LCC (life cycle costing) could also be improved. Thus, diverse methodologies, tools, and databases need to be further developed to improve the comprehensiveness of LCA-guided contributions to SSbD assessments. TRL 4-6.

Co-creation gaps: Research gaps 5, 6 and 7.

Research gap 5: Test, adapt and co-create SSbD assessment-methods and -outcomes in terms of their efficacy in supporting decision-making relative to the sustainability transition processes in the chemical sector. An effective, comprehensive and validated approach asks for further optimization, adoption and implementation of SSbD assessment tools. Research focusing on improving SSbD assessment based on practical case studies can support this. Co-creation partners and relevant stakeholders in the case studies should include, among others: (large and small) chemical companies and manufacturers, complemented with ESG-accounting and -audit experts; institutional investors; banks, ESG evaluators and market experts; NGOs; and Global Green Finance as well as the sustainable finance taxonomy experts outside the EU to provide input relative to the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). TRL 5-7.

Research gap 6: Develop a better understanding of socio-economic factors that influence reciprocal interactions between chemicals and people. In the context of equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations, research is needed on how chemicals may affect communities differently, and how different people would address and solve health and environmental problems with chemicals, depending on i) ancestries, ii) gender identities, iii) life stories and iv) socio-economic differential exposure. Based on insights from research into socio-ecological systems, the societal interpretation of SSbD needs and results will vary. This may result in different ‘solutions pathways’ including divergent timelines, depending on the region. Therefore, instead of an assumed ‘one-size-fits-all’ use of SSbD-principles and -outcomes, it should be acknowledged that different solution pathways may yield optimal results under different conditions. Development of such solution pathways should also take into account the multidimensional perspectives for human populations (e.g., geographical aspects that can influence both exposure to threats and access to training). TRL 3-5.

Research gap 7: Education, training and skills. There is a clear need for developing EU-wide Masters and PhD programmes that integrate horizontal knowledge and understanding across disciplines related to chemical safety assessment, including hazard, exposure and risk assessment, LCA and SSbD. Cross-sectoral learning - such as the SSbD-wide use of tiering to improve the utility of LCA, as suggested in Research gap 3 - is considered highly beneficial for SSbD implementation. In addition, multidisciplinary teams must be developed with experts from sustainability and safety domains originating from industry, government, and academia to co-create the educational outreach to professionals and students on SSbD implementation. This would ensure an efficient build-up of resources, including capability and capacity to translate the SSbD vision into reality. TRL 7-9.

Next steps: The SETAC-Europe sounding board welcomes further discussion and elaboration of the identified opportunities, recommendations and research gaps, and looks forward to continuing the discussion with the EC DG RTD to accelerate implementation of a sound, robust and accurate SSbD framework that would effectively support a sustainable transition of the chemical sector in Europe under the Green Deal. SETAC will, in the meantime, be progressing the science around the SSbD concepts and practice.

References

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SETAC-EC Consultation series report 2: Annegaike Leopold, Michelle Bloor, Bruno Campos, Evangelis Daskalopoulos, Ksenia Groh, Leo Posthuma, Serenella Sala, Hans Sanderson, Hanna Schreiber, Christoph Schür, Paul Thomas. Preliminary report of the 2nd Consultation meeting on CSS/SSbD, January 31, 2024. https://www.setac.org/resource/preliminary-rep-2nd-consultation-meeting_final-pdf.html

SETAC-EC Consultation series report 3: Leo Posthuma, Michelle Bloor, Bruno Campos, Ksenia Groh, Leo Posthuma, Christoph Schür, Paul Thomas, Hans Sanderson and Annegaike Leopold (2024) Conceptual and practical approaches to improve the utility of SSbD Assessments - Preliminary insights from SETAC-EC online Consultations and an onsite Workshop in Seville, May 6, 2024. https://www.setac.org/resource/workshop-report-seville_preliminary-insights-from-setac-ec-online-consultations-pdf.html

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